

A Comprehensive Kinetic Study on Interaction of Cobalt(II) and Copper(II) with 1-Methylglycocyanidine

H. C. MALHOTRA*, AMITABH K. JAIN AND VOGESHWAR SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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The kinetics of the reaction between Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with 1-methyl glycocyanidine has been studied in the pH range 6.32–7.32 and 1.68–3.47 respectively, in 0.3 M KNO_3 and at 25, 30, 35 and $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$ by stopped-flow spectrophotometer. The experimental rate constants obtained, have been resolved into stepwise rate constants, and activation parameters corresponding to each pathway has been determined. The hydrolysed form of metal ion i.e. MOH^+ , was found to be more reactive than M^{2+} form.

1-Methylglycocyanidine (creatinine) is an important constituent of mature erythrocytes and is used by physiological systems for clearance of excess metal ions through urine¹. A study² on toxic side-effects upon drug administration in animals was found due to decreased filtering capacity of kidney, consequently elevating the blood urea nitrogen and decreased creatinine clearance of metal ions. This particular problem was overcome by injecting metal-creatinine complexes in rats and mouse. Metal creatinine complexes were also found³ effective in eliminating the side effects and toxicity of anticancer drugs like cisplatin. The reactions of metal ions with amino acids of this type have been a subject of several kinetic investigations with widely varying results⁴⁻⁶. Mentasti *et al.*⁶ found it necessary to propose hydrolysed metal (MOH^+) as a reactive species whereas others⁴⁻⁵, at much higher pH's, did not think so.

With these anomalies and ambiguities, we have undertaken a kinetic study on the reaction of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with 1-methylglycocyanidine in order to understand clearly the complex biological process of creatinine clearance.

Experimental

1-Methylglycocyanidine (SISCO), bromothymol blue (BDH), $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (both Merck) were used as such. Other chemicals were A.R. grade.

pH of the solutions were adjusted using 2,6-lutidine (Merck Schuchardt) and HCl (Glaxo, A.R.) in case of Co^{II} -1-methylglycocyanidine interaction and NaOH/ HNO_3 in case of Cu^{II} -1-methylglycocyanidine interaction. There was a slight change in pH (~0.05 units) after mixing and the pH values reported are those of the reaction mixtures. The final pH was taken on a Radiometer M 26 pH meter. Temperature of the system was maintained by a NBE (Germany) immersion type thermostat.

The kinetic runs were made on a Aminco-Morrow stopped-flow spectrophotometer under

pseudo-first order conditions, i.e. $[\text{M}(\text{II})] \gg [1\text{-methylglycocyanidine}]$. The absorbance changes were monitored at 620 nm for Co^{II} -1-methylglycocyanidine interaction by pH indicator method⁴ and at 600 nm for Cu^{II} -1-methylglycocyanidine interaction without any indicator as the absorbance changes were large enough to be monitored directly.

The values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k'_{obs}) were evaluated from the slopes of plots of $\log \Delta V$ vs time ($\Delta V = (V_\infty - V_0)/(V_\infty - V_t)$). The values of second order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated (Table 1) using the relation $k_{\text{obs}} = k'_{\text{obs}}/[\text{M}(\text{II})]$.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE INTERACTION OF Co^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH 1-METHYL GLYCOCYANIDINE AT DIFFERENT pH AND TEMPERATURES

$\mu = 0.3 \text{ M KNO}_3$, [1-methyl glycocyanidine] = $1.24 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ for Co^{II} , ($[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}] = 1.66 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) and $1.22 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ for Cu^{II} ($[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 1.64 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$)

Co ^{II} -1-methyl glycocyanidine		Cu ^{II} -1-methyl glycocyanidine	
pH	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	pH	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Temp. = $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$			
6.31	1.90	1.68	1.01
6.43	2.10	1.90	1.16
6.62	2.56	2.38	1.28
6.78	3.16	2.42	1.52
6.88	6.12	2.47	3.07
6.94	7.38	2.66	3.53
7.02	10.2	2.94	5.18
7.11	12.6	3.19	6.16
7.32	17.7	3.47	9.77
Temp. = $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$			
6.29	4.10	1.72	2.56
6.42	7.22	1.86	3.62
6.66	8.10	2.26	4.05
6.78	9.16	2.37	6.28
6.84	10.0	2.42	7.72
6.95	12.3	2.68	7.79
7.07	15.1	2.77	10.2
7.18	21.0	2.96	12.8
7.22	27.8	3.10	16.9
7.26	30.5	3.21	20.2
		3.44	21.7

(Table 1 contd.)

Temp. = 35 ± 0.05°			
6.22	9.92	1.82	4.80
6.45	12.5	1.96	5.20
6.66	15.9	2.09	7.77
6.78	17.7	2.37	8.76
6.89	19.8	2.44	10.2
6.94	21.2	2.66	12.0
7.00	24.7	2.94	12.2
7.08	27.8	3.07	15.1
7.12	32.0	3.18	19.8
7.19	41.2	3.26	23.7
7.27	49.8	3.46	28.3

Temp. = 40 ± 0.05°			
6.23	15.9	1.90	7.75
6.36	18.8	1.92	9.20
6.67	24.8	2.37	11.9
6.69	28.7	2.46	13.8
6.88	34.8	2.52	17.2
6.94	38.6	2.69	17.8
6.99	44.2	2.99	23.0
7.07	59.8	3.07	29.1
7.12	64.7	3.22	33.1
7.24	77.5	3.37	38.7

Results and Discussions

The data in Table 1 was tried with Scheme 1, normally applicable to such complexation reactions,

Here HL⁺ and L represent the protonated and deprotonated form of the ligand respectively. This scheme leads to equation⁴ (1),

$$k_{obs} \frac{K_a + [H^+]}{[H^+]} = k_1 + \frac{k_2 K_a}{[H^+]} \quad (1)$$

Since [H⁺] ≫ K_a (3.1 × 10⁻¹¹), a plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺]⁻¹ is expected to be a straight line. This plot for Co^{II}-1-methylglycocyanidine interaction is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that at high pH the

Fig. 1. Plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺]⁻¹ for the interaction of Co^{II} with 1-methylglycocyanidine.

intercept of the line changes although the slope remains same.

The data was next tried with Scheme 2, proposed by Mentasti *et al.*^{5,6} who considered hydrolysed metal ion as a reactive species.

The observed rate has been resolved into stepwise rate constants on the basis of this scheme, as given by equation (2),

$$k_{obs} = k_1 K_a + \frac{k_2 K_a K_M}{[H^+]} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) again fails to explain two intercepts and the scheme does not consider the interaction of deprotonated form of the ligand.

However, the Scheme 3, suggested by Malhotra and Jain⁷, was found to explain the data very well.

The rate for the reaction between metal ions and 1-methylglycocyanidine is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} &= k_{obs} [M(II)]_T [1\text{-Methylglycocyanidine}]_T \\
 &= k_{obs} \{ [MH_2O^{3+}] + [MOH^+] \} \{ [LH^+] + [L] \} \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

As evident from Scheme 3 the rate can also be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} &= k_1 [MH_2O^{3+}] [LH^+] + k_2 [MH_2O^{3+}] [L] \\
 &+ k_3 [MOH^+] [LH^+] + k_4 [MOH^+] [L] \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

If it is assumed that in the low pH region (MOH⁺), hydrolysed metal concentration is very low then the terms containing MOH⁺ can be ignored, and equations (3) and (4) on combining yield

$$k_{obs} \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_a}{[H^+]} \right\} = k_1 + k_2 \frac{K_a}{[H^+]} \quad (5)$$

At a higher pH when MOH⁺ is comparable to MH₂O³⁺, which is usually the case¹⁰, the observed rate constant from equations (3) and (4) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_{obs} \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_M}{[H^+]} \right\} \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_a}{[H^+]} \right\} &= k_1 + k_2 K_M \\
 &+ \frac{k_3 K_a + k_4 K_M K_a}{[H^+]} \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

Since K_a and K_M are very less compared to $[H^+]$, equations (5) and (6) reduce respectively to equations (7) and (8),

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_2 \frac{K_a}{[H^+]} \quad (7)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_3 K_M + \frac{k_2 K_a}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_4 K_M K_a}{[H^+]} \quad (8)$$

It can also be seen from Fig. 1 that the slope does not change at all and if the above assumptions are correct then k_4 always must be zero. This is supported by the fact that MOH^+ is generally non-reactive towards non-hydrogen bonded ligands⁹.

So the final equations are

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + \frac{k_2 K_a}{[H^+]}$$

in low pH region and

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_3 K_M + \frac{k_2 K_a}{[H^+]}$$

in high pH region.

The values of k_1 , k_2 and k_3 at different temperatures were calculated by linear least-square fit analysis of the data in Table 1. k_1 was evaluated from intercept, k_2 from slope and k_3 from difference in intercepts at high and low pH regions. The values are reported along with activation parameters, evaluated from linear plots of $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$, in Table 2.

The values of K_a^0 and K_M^0 were corrected for the desired temperatures using the thermodynamic relation,

$$\log K_b^{T_2} = \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger (T_2 - T_1)}{4.6 T_1 T_2} + \log K_b^{T_1} \quad (9)$$

where $b = a$ or M .

The values of k_1 and k_2 (Table 2) in case of the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} compare well with the earlier determined values^{3,4,11} and k_3 is expected¹¹ to be 10^2 to 10^4 times faster than k_2 . This is contrary to expectations as the charge on complexing metal ion

is less in step k_3 . The enhancement in the rate can be explained on the basis of strong labilising influence of the OH^- on the remaining water molecules¹² in metal ions inner coordination sphere.

The dissociation of 1-methylglycocyanidene can be represented as

The complexing of $M(II)$ by 1-methylglycocyanidene takes place through both the forms of ligand as evidenced from values of k_2 and k_3 (Table 2). The mechanism of complex formation can now be written as

From the above mechanism it is very much clear that the metal ion is enclosed in a cage-like structure after complexation and cannot interact with any other enzyme, amino acid or proteins and peptides or tissues and cells to cause any carcinogenic activity. The faster rates and cage-like structure thus suggest the increased clearance of metal ions through urine, thereby normalising the blood urea nitrogen level. Our investigations are thus helpful in understanding the mechanism of removal of toxic side-effects of metal ions in physiological systems.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF STEPWISE RATE CONSTANTS AND THEIR ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE INTERACTION OF Co^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH 1-METHYL GLYCOCYANIDENE

Temp. $\pm 0.05^\circ C$	Co^{II} -1-methyl glycocyanidene			Cu^{II} -1-methyl glycocyanidene		
	k_1 $\times 10$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	k_2 $\times 10^{-6}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	k_3 $\times 10^{-10}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	k_1 $\times 10$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	k_2 $\times 10^{-10}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	k_3 $\times 10^{-14}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$
25	0.00	6.25	2.90	0.22	3.27	1.42
30	1.77	6.86	7.58	0.86	3.96	3.91
35	4.52	8.58	17.2	2.88	4.88	8.56
40	11.7	10.9	40.9	5.96	5.92	18.2
ΔH^\ddagger (kcal mol ⁻¹)	18.6 ± 0.2	3.52 ± 0.22	14.1 ± 0.7	9.88 ± 0.86	1.96 ± 0.12	12.0 ± 0.3
ΔS^\ddagger cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	27.7 ± 0.9	-9.82 ± 0.11	16.2 ± 0.7	26.7 ± 0.1	-12.8 ± 0.7	9.07 ± 0.18

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